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EXTRACT DATA IN LARGE DATABASE WITH HADOOP

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Abstract:

Data is basic building block of any organization and extracting useful information from raw available data is the big task and high complexity task. Data are the patterns which are used to develop or enhance knowledge. The rapid growth in the size of datasets that are collected from different resources has made capturing, managing and analyzing the datasets beyond the ability of most software tools. The current methodologies and data mining software tools cannot manage the current growth of datasets and extracting knowledge. With the advancement in information technology starting from file system to Object Oriented database, now it has reached to Data Warehouse and Data Marts. But every piece of data stored in these databases may not be useful for the decision purpose. Organizations need to filter the useful data from bulk of data which can be used for decision making, reporting or analysis. Big Data mining is the capacity of extracting useful information from these large datasets or social networking datasets, that due to its volume, variability, and velocity, it was not answer with the available methodology. Hadoop is an open source project, and pioneered a fundamentally a new way of storing and processing data.

Keywords: Big Data, Hadoop, Data Warehouse

Introduction

During the last several decades, dramatic advances in computing power, storage, and networking technology have allowed the human race to generate, process, and share increasing amounts of information in dramatically new ways. As new applications of computing technology are developed and introduced, these applications are often used in ways that their designers never envisioned. New applications, in turn, lead to new demands for even more powerful computing infrastructure [1]. To meet these computing-infrastructure demands, system designers are constantly looking for new system architectures and algorithms to process larger collections of data more quickly than is feasible with today's systems. It is now possible to assemble very large, powerful systems consisting of many small, inexpensive commodity components because computers have become smaller and less expensive, disk drive capacity continues to increase, and networks have gotten faster. Such systems tend to be much less costly than a single, faster machine with comparable capabilities. Currently the data set sizes for applications are growing in an incredible manner [2]. Thus the data sets growing beyond the few hundreds of terabytes, have no solutions to manage and analyse these data. Services like social networking approaches to achieve the goals like minimum amount of effort in terms of software, CPU and network. Cloud computing is associated with the new paradigm for provisioning the computing infrastructure. Thus the paradigm shifts the location of infrastructure to the network to reduce the cost associated with the management of hardware and software resources. The cloud computing is said to be as the model for enabling convenient, on-

demand network access, to a shared pool of configurable computing resources that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction.

The issue of the measurement of three evaluation dimensions simultaneously has led to another important issue in data stream mining, namely estimating the combined cost of performing the learning and prediction processes in terms of time and memory. As an example, several rental cost options exist.

- Cost per hour of usage: Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud (Amazon EC2) is a web service that provides resizable compute capacity in the cloud. Cost depends on the time and on the machine rented (small instance with 1.7 GB, large with 7.5 GB or extra large with 15GB)[1].
- Cost per hour and memory used: GoGrid is a web service similar to Amazon EC2, but it charges by RAM Hours. Every GB of RAM deployed for 1 hour equals one RAM-Hour.

Hadoop is a framework for running large number of applications which consists HDFS for storing large number of dataset. Hadoop DB tries to achieve fault tolerance and the ability to operate in heterogeneous environments by inheriting the scheduling and job tracking implementation from Hadoop [3]. The main aim of these systems is to improve the performance through parallelization of various operations such as loading the datasets, index building and evaluating the queries. These systems usually designed to run on top of a shared nothing architecture where data may be stored in a distributed fashion and input/output speeds are improved by using multiple CPU's disk in parallel and network links with high available bandwidth.

Hadoop database tries to achieve the performance of parallel databases by doing most of query processing inside the database engine. Hadoop is an open source and framework that is used in cloud environment for efficient data analysis and storage of data. It supports data-intensive applications by realizing the implementation of the Map Reduce framework. Inspired by the Google's architecture. Integration of Hadoop and Hive is used to store and retrieve the dataset in a efficient manner. For more efficiency of data storage and transactions of retail business the integration of Hadoop ecosystem with HBase along with the cloud environment is used to store and retrieve the data sets persistently. The performance analysis is done with the Map Reduce parameters like HBase heap memory and Caching parameter.

Big Data

Data Warehouse

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Hadoop

Hadoop is an open source project which was implemented in Java. Hadoop provides a framework for distributed computing using Map Reduce programming model. As a framework, it needs support with implementation projects such as Mahout and Hive, which are run on top of Hadoop for mining big data[5]. Mahout and Hive projects have implementations for data mining algorithms and techniques which are presented in the

tutorial. RHive package has been proposed at the end of the tutorial as a solution for analysts who are not interested in Java programming.

Hive

Hive is a system for querying and managing large datasets residing in distributed storage. Hive provides a mechanism to project structure onto this data and query the data using a SQL-like language called HiveQL. At the same time this language also allows traditional map/reduce programmers to plug in their custom mappers and reducers when it is inconvenient or inefficient to express this logic in HiveQL.

Hive QL

Hive QL is the tuple subset of the hive data warehousing. It makes use of the parser for execution of the map reduce program and to store the large data set in HDFS of Hadoop.

Map Reduce

Map Reduce is a programming model for processing large data sets, and the implementation is done with the Google. Map Reduce is typically used to do distribute computing on clusters of computers. Map Reduce is a framework for processing parallelizable problems across huge datasets using a large number of computers (nodes), collectively referred to as a cluster (if all nodes are on the same local network and use.

"Map" step:

The master node takes the input, divides it into smaller sub-problems, and distributes them to worker nodes. A worker node may do this again in turn, leading to a multi-level tree structure. The worker node processes the smaller problem, and passes the answer back to its master node.

"Reduce" step:

The master node then collects the answers to all the sub-problems and combines them in some way to form the output – the answer to the problem it was originally trying to solve.

1. **Prepare the Map() input** – the Map Reduce system designates Map processors, assigns the K1 input key value each processor would work on, and provides that processor with all the input data associated with that key value.
2. **Run the user-provided Map() code** – Map() is run exactly once for each K1 key value, generating output organized by key values K2.
3. **Shuffle the Map output to the Reduce processors** – the Map Reduce system designates Reduce processors, assigns the K2 key value each processor should work on, and provides that processor with all the Map-generated data associated with that key value.
4. **Run the user-provided Reduce() code** – Reduce() is run exactly once for each K2 key value produced by the Map step.
5. **Produce the final output** – the Map Reduce system collects all the Reduce output, and sorts it by K2 to produce the final outcome.

HDFS

Hadoop Distributed File System cluster consists of a single Name node, a master server that manages the file system namespace and regulates access to files by clients. There are a number of Data Nodes usually one per node in a cluster. The Data Nodes manage storage attached to the nodes that they run on. HDFS contains a file system namespace and allows user data to be stored in files. A single file is being split into one or more blocks and set of blocks are stored in Data Nodes.

Figure 1.1 How Hadoop Works

Figure 1.2 Real world Hadoop implementation

III. CLUSTERED STORAGE

A Hadoop cluster is commonly referred to as shared nothing. One of the things that distinguishes HDFS from some of the more common file systems like NFS and CIFS is its ability to support a distributed computing, shared nothing architecture.

Shared nothing means almost exactly what it says. In a distributed computing cluster composed of parallelized nodes, the only thing that's actually shared is the cluster network that interconnects the compute nodes. Nothing else is shared, including storage, which is implemented as disk-based Direct-Attached Storage (DAS). Usually DAS here consists of one set of eight to 10 disks per node configured as RAID or JBOD for maximum performance. Solid-State Drives (SSDs) aren't typically used because of cost.

One of the objectives of the shared nothing paradigm is to reduce processing latency. Keep in mind that we want to process queries that grind through an enormous amount of data, often in five seconds or less. So minimizing cluster-wide latency is a critical priority for Hadoop developers and system architects.

Figure. 3.1 Processes large jobs in parallel across many nodes

I. CONCLUSION

Big Data is going to continue growing during the next years, and each data scientist will have to manage much more amount of data every year. This data is going to be more diverse, larger, and faster. Thus the Hadoop Ecosystem with the integration of Hbase database should be used in various fields like telecommunications, banks, insurance, medical fields etc. To maintain the public details in an efficient manner and to avoid the fraudulent [2]. There is no doubt that data stream mining offers many challenges and equally many opportunities as the quantity of data generated in real time is going to continue growing.

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